

Original article

Clinical manifestations of paediatric severe falciparum malaria at a reference hospital in Azare, northeastern Nigeria.

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Abstract

Background: The scourge of malaria endures. Globally, 249 million cases were documented in 2022 with Nigeria accounting for the highest figure. The severe complications of falciparum malaria and their relative impact on treatment outcome have largely been studied. However, these studies are yet to be replicated in our region. **Objectives:** This study evaluated the spectrum of complications of falciparum malaria, the impact of parasite count on the development of complications and the impact of age, complications and parasite count on treatment outcome in children managed at the Emergency Paediatric Unit of the Federal University of Health Sciences Teaching Hospital Azare, Bauchi state. **Materials and Methods:** This was a retrospective study of children managed for severe falciparum malaria from 1st September 2021 to 31st December 2022. Analysis of data was done with IBM SPSS version 20. **Results:** Two hundred and ninety-six children were studied. The male to female ratio was 1.49: 1. The mean age was 5.52 years, that for boys differed significantly from that for girls ($p = 0.01$). Patients with cerebral malaria were most likely to stay for longer periods on admission ($p = <0.0001$). Complications of severe falciparum malaria significantly impacted outcome ($p = <0.0001$) and cerebral malaria was the most fatal complication of falciparum malaria. However, age and parasite count had no significant impact on outcome ($p = 0.53$ respectively). Similarly, parasite count had no impact on the relative development of complications ($p = 0.69$). **Conclusion:** The complications of falciparum malaria significantly impacted patient outcome.

Keywords: Cerebral malaria, Complications, Falciparum, Outcome, Severe malaria.

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ISSN: Print; 2992-555X Electronic: 3092-9865

<https://doi.org/>

Date Submitted 16th March, 2025

Date Accepted 28th June 2025

Date Published 30th June, 2025

Cited this article as: Iragbogie A. Imoudu, Maimuna O. Yusuf. **Clinical Manifestations of Paediatric Severe Falciparum Malaria at a Reference Hospital in Azare, Northeastern Nigeria.** *The Scholar J Health Scie* 2025; 1(1): 72-79.

Introduction

According to the most recent global figures the scourge of malaria lingers on.¹ Globally, 249,000,000 cases were documented in 2022 with Nigeria accounting for 66,722,000 of these; the highest from any nation.¹ Severe malaria remains the fatal form of the disease, and it accounted for 462,080 deaths in children under the age of five years. About 177,901 children below the age of five years died of severe falciparum malaria in Nigeria in 2022.¹

The severe complications of falciparum malaria and their relative impact on treatment outcome have largely been studied.^{2,3} However, major geographical and genetic differences occur in complication rates and relative prognosis.^{2,4} Furthermore, the impact of parasite burden on the complications and prognosis of malaria is still contentious.⁵⁻⁷ There is a paucity of data on these subjects in our region. Hence there was a need to identify local complications, treatment outcome and the impact of parasite count on the prognosis of severe malaria.

This study evaluated the spectrum of complications of falciparum malaria as well as the impact of age,

complications and parasite count on treatment outcome in children managed at the emergency paediatric unit (EPU) of the Federal University of Health Sciences Teaching Hospital, Azare (FUHSTHA)- formally Federal Medical Centre Azare, Bauchi state. The impact of parasite count on the relative development of complications was also assessed.

Materials and Methods

Institutional ethical clearance was obtained from the Research Ethics and Review Committee of the Federal Medical Centre, Azare, Bauchi state (later FUHSTHA). This was a retrospective study. Records of all patients diagnosed with and managed for severe malaria at the EPU of FUHSTHA were retrieved and the following information were obtained and entered into a self-designed proforma: Age in years (from last birthday), gender, father's highest educational qualification, date of admission, date of discharge, complication of malaria, parasite count, and treatment outcome. The period under review was from 1st September, 2021 to 31st December, 2022, a 16-month period. A diagnosis of severe malaria was confirmed in all cases by either examination of thick and thin blood films of malaria parasite (MP) or malaria rapid diagnostic test (mRDT). The mRDT for detecting Plasmodium falciparum histidine-rich protein 2 (PfHRP2) was applied.⁸ The definitions of severe malaria and management of cases were done as per National guidelines.⁹

Statistical analysis

Analysis of the collected data was done with IBM SPSS version 20. The presentation of data was done in prose, figures and tables. Means \pm standard deviations were computed for continuous data. Means were compared with the T test or one-way ANOVA as appropriate while categorical variables were compared with the Chi-square test. A p value < 0.05 was regarded as statistically significant.

Results

Two hundred and ninety-six children were managed in the EPU for severe malaria during the period under review, amounting to 8.38% of the total number of patients (3533) managed during the same period. One hundred and seventy-seven boys (59.8%) and 119 (40.2%) girls were managed for severe malaria, giving a male to female ratio of 1.49:1. Majority of the children were under five years of age (60.8%). The mean age for boys (4.92 ± 3.52 years) differed significantly from that for girls (6.4 ± 3.78 years), $p = 0.01$. Table 1 displays the characteristics of the study participants.

Table 1. Characteristics of Study Participants.

Characteristic	Frequency	Percentage(%)
Age (years)		
< 1	15	5.1
1-5	165	55.7
6-10	77	26.0
11-16	39	13.2
Mean age (years)	5.52 \pm 3.8	
Gender		
Male	177	59.8
Female	119	40.2
Parasite count		
1+	103	34.8
2+	65	22.0
3+	22	7.4
4+	0	0.0
Not seen	106	35.8
Outcome		
Complete recovery	270	91.2
Discharged with sequelae	3	1.0
DAMA	3	1.0
Death	20	6.8

DAMA- Discharged against medical advice, 1+ - 1-10 parasites/100 thick film fields, 2+ - 1-10 parasites/10 thick film fields, 3+ - 1-10 parasites/thick film field, 4+ - > 10 parasites/thick film field

Fig 1 outlines the age distribution of severe malaria. The youngest child diagnosed with severe malaria was a 2-month-old boy and the eldest a 16-year-old girl. The modal age was two years.

Fig 1. Age distribution of severe falciparum malaria

Fig 2 shows the spectrum of complications diagnosed in the study participants superimposed on the mean number of admission days. Patients with cerebral malaria were most likely to stay for longer periods on admission, $p = 0.000$.

Fig 2. Distribution of severe falciparum malaria by mean number of admission days.

Table 2 shows the impact of age, malaria complications and parasite count on treatment outcome. The complications significantly impacted

treatment outcome, $p = 0.000$. The case fatality rate was 6.76%.

Table 2. Impact of age, complications and parasite count on outcome

% Features	Outcome					p value	
	Complete recovery (%)	Discharged with sequelae (%)	DAMA(%)	Death(%)	Total(%)		
Age (years)							
<1	14(4.7)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	1(0.3)	15(5.1)	0.53	
1-5	145(49.0)	2(0.7)	3(1.0)	15(5.1)	165(55.7)		
6-10	74(25.0)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	3(1.0)	77(26.0)		
11-16	37(12.5)	1(0.3)	0(0.0)	1(0.3)	39(13.2)		
Complications of malaria							
Prostration	91(30.7)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	91(30.7)	0.00	
Cerebral malaria	47(15.9)	2(0.7)	2(0.7)	12(4.1)	63(21.3)		
Cerebral malaria with severe anaemia	3(1.0)	1(0.3)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	4(1.4)		
Severe anaemia	38(12.8)	0(0.0)	1(0.3)	5(1.7)	44(14.9)		
Severe anaemia with hyperbilirubinaemia	2(0.7)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	2 (0.7)		
Hyperbilirubinaemia	4(1.4)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	4(1.4)		
Multiple convulsions	79(26.7)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	2(0.7)	81(27.4)		
Severe anaemia with multiple convulsions	4(1.4)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	4(1.4)		
Hypoglycaemia	1(0.3)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	1(0.3)		
Hyperbilirubinaemia with multiple convulsions	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	1(0.3)	1(0.3)		
Severe anaemia with haemoglobinuria and Hyperbilirubinaemia	1(0.3)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	1(0.3)		
Parasite count							
1+	95(32.1)	1(0.3)	2(0.7)	5(1.7)	103(34.8)		0.899
2+	60(20.3)	1(0.3)	0(0.0)	4(1.4)	65(22.0)		
3+	21(7.1)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	1(0.3)	22(7.4)		
4+	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)		
Not seen	94(31.8)	1(0.3)	1(0.3)	10(3.4)	106(35.8)		

DAMA- Discharged against medical advice, 1+ - 1-10 parasites/100 thick film fields, 2+ - 1-10 parasites/10 thick film fields, 3+ - 1-10 parasites/ thick film field, 4+ - > 10 parasites/thick film field.

Fig 3 demonstrates that parasite count had no significant impact on the relative development of complications of falciparum malaria, ($\chi^2= 25.75$, $df= 30$, $p = 0.69$).

Figure 3. Distribution of severe malaria by parasite density.

Discussion

We set up to evaluate the spectrum of falciparum malaria complications, the impact of age, falciparum malaria complications and parasite count on treatment outcome as well as the impact of parasite count on the relative development of complications. Our findings indicated a wide spectrum of falciparum malaria complications and that these complications had a scientifically significant impact on treatment outcome in this study. There was, however, no significant relationship between parasite count and relative development of complications of falciparum malaria in this cohort of patients.

There were seven complications of falciparum malaria encountered in this study. These complications mostly occurred in isolation but in a few instances also occurred in combinations of two or three at a time in the same patient. The most frequent was prostration followed by multiple convulsions while hypoglycaemia, hyperbilirubinaemia and haemoglobinuria were the least frequent. These findings are largely similar to previous reports from other centres within Nigeria and other parts of sub-Saharan Africa.¹⁰⁻¹² However, certain differences were observed in the proportions of complications; severe malarial anaemia which featured quite prominently in an Enugu study,¹⁰ was fourth in ranking in terms of

occurrence in the present study. Also, respiratory distress was not demonstrated in our study. In addition, cerebral malaria occurred less frequently in East and Central African studies.^{11,12} Reasons for these disparities are beyond the scope of this study, yet they may be due to the fact that the children involved here were mostly below the age of 5 years unlike in the aforementioned reports. Also, severe malarial anaemia (SMA) is thought to be relatively less common in severely malnourished children and the fact that Northeastern Nigeria has the country's highest prevalence of severe acute malnutrition may explain the relatively low occurrence of SMA in this study.^{13,14}

Cerebral malaria was overwhelmingly the most fatal complication in this study, sketchily followed by SMA. This is consistent with findings from a wide range of sources.¹⁵⁻¹⁷ Clearly explaining why cerebral malaria is the most lethal complication of malaria remains a challenging task, however, it may speculatively be linked to the extensive neurologic damage associated with the condition.^{18,19} Age and parasite count had no significant impact on outcome in the present review. Age was also not significantly associated with outcome as reported by Jalo et al in Gombe, North eastern Nigeria.¹⁵ Nevertheless, there are several other reports indicating a vital impact for age on the outcome of severe malaria.^{20,21} An explanation for our discordant finding is not readily available, nonetheless, one could posit that variations in outcome definition and residual confounding (e.g., comorbidities, nutritional status) may have obscured the age-outcome relationship. Parasite density was also not associated with outcome in a Tanzanian study,⁶ but associated with an unfavourable outcome in Pakistan.⁷ Prior home treatment in the present study participants may have accounted for this discrepancy.

Parasite count had no relevant relationship with the relative development of complications of falciparum malaria in this study. This is not at variance with other reports.^{6,22} However, these studies demonstrated a significant influence of parasite density on severe malaria occurring, but higher parasite levels did not equate to the development of more severe complications nor did it suggest the occurrence of the least severe ones. Still, Alli et al,⁷ found a significant relationship between parasite density and relative development of complications of falciparum malaria. This dissimilarity may have stemmed from the fact that the present study utilized parasite counts in estimating parasite burden in contrast to the latter study which utilized parasite density as

determined by the percentage of parasitized red blood cells.

This study has outlined the spectrum of complications of falciparum malaria seen in our setting and also demonstrated that these complications had a significant bearing on treatment outcome. Yet, there were limitations to the study. They include the fact that a retrospective approach was applied in the study (a longitudinal prospective design would have been more suitable), and parasite burden determined with parasite density rather than the plus system would have been better fitted. Also, a multicentre approach would have strengthened the findings made. Future studies in addition, may focus on improving treatment outcomes for the most fatal complications of falciparum malaria and on identifying the spectrum of clinical biomarkers of severity as well as their impact on outcome.

Conclusion

The complications of falciparum malaria in this part of Nigeria are similar to those found in other areas. These complications significantly impacted patient outcome, with cerebral malaria being the most fatal. However, age and parasite count had no impact on treatment outcome.

Recommendation

Health education on the need for early presentation and prompt institution of management particularly for cerebral malaria would significantly improve outcome.

Acknowledgement

We are thankful to Dr. Shaibu P and Mr. Ahmad MI for participating in data collection.

Authors' contributions: Imoudu IA developed the conceptualized and designed the study. He also analysed and interpreted the data and drafted the article. Yusuf MO contributed to data collection and study design. Both authors reviewed and approved the final manuscript.

Conflict of interests: None

Funding: None

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